

Tailoring cryopreservation protocols for chicken sperm of poor freezing breeds.

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Cryopreservation is a valuable tool for preserving the biodiversity of farm animals, a crucial issue in tackling climate change and meeting future nutritional demands. However, the cryopreservation of chicken sperm is still in the development phase. The low cryo-resistance of sperm from several native breeds can result in very low sperm quality and fertility rates. The demonstrated dependence between cryotolerance and chicken breed seems to indicate the need to adapt cryopreservation protocols to the native breed of interest. On the other hand, the contraceptive effect of glycerol (the best cryoprotectant for chicken sperm) in the hen makes it necessary to find alternative cryoprotectants. In previous work by our group, in which dimethylacetamide (DMA) was used as a cryoprotectant to freeze semen from broiler-breed roosters, valuable knowledge was gained about the favourable conditions for obtaining optimal sperm motility and viability. Based on this knowledge the present work proposed a cryopreservation protocol (total sperm dilution 1:3, DMA 0.6 M, one-step static deep-freezing $\approx 100^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, package 0.5 ml straws) to freeze sperm collected from Yellow Hungarian roosters (YH), a native breed that responds bad to freezing. Due to the low sperm concentration of YH, the dilution ratio of the pre-frozen YH sperm had to be decreased with respect to that originally indicated by the protocol. Thus, one aliquot of the collected samples was subjected to the required dilution (Treatment 1), while the dilution ratio of the second aliquot was reduced to less than half (Treatment 2). The effect of the dilution ratio on semen quality after thawing was evaluated. In addition, YH semen was frozen using the usual protocol (pre-freezing dilution ratio 1:1, 6% DMA, 2 steps static deep-freezing, package 0.25 ml straw) (Treatment 3), to compare it with treatments 1 and 2. The parameters evaluated to compare the three treatments were: viability (live spermatozoa), abnormalities, total motility, progressive motility, acrosome integrity and DNA integrity. The results indicated that treatment 1 was the best protocol. The viability of treatment 1 (56.7 ± 3.0) improved compared to treatment 3 (42.8 ± 4.7). In terms of abnormalities, treatment 2 had a higher number of abnormal sperm (19.1 ± 1.6) than treatments 1 (15.4 ± 1.0) and 3 (12.0 ± 1.4), while no differences were observed between treatments 1 and 3, indicating that, in this breed, more diluted semen is needed to obtain better sperm quality. The low sperm concentration of the frozen samples with treatment 1 should be compensated for by increasing the days of artificial insemination. Subsequent artificial insemination trials will reveal whether this improvement in sperm quality, together with the increase in the frequency of insemination, are sufficient to improve the fertility rate obtained with the usual freezing protocol (Treatment 3).